

Evaluations of *In vitro* Thrombolytic and *In vivo* Cardio Protective Activities of Methanolic Seeds Extract of *Celastrus paniculatus*

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Abstract

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a major cause of global mortality, with myocardial infarction and thromboembolic events contributing significantly to morbidity. The present study aimed to evaluate the *in vitro* thrombolytic and *in vivo* cardioprotective activities of the methanolic seed extract of *Celastrus paniculatus* Willd. (CPSE). Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, tannins, saponins, and steroids, indicating strong antioxidant potential. The *in vitro* thrombolytic activity was assessed using human blood clot models with streptokinase as standard, showing significant concentration-dependent clots lysis. Acute oral toxicity studies (OECD 423) revealed no toxic symptoms up to 2000 mg/kg, indicating a favorable safety profile. The *in vivo* cardioprotective activity was evaluated in rats using isoproterenol (ISO)-induced myocardial infarction (85 mg/kg, *s.c.* on the 20th and 21st days). CPSE was administered orally at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg for 21 days. ISO control rats exhibited elevated cardiac biomarkers (CK-MB, LDH, AST, ALT, and troponin I), lipid abnormalities, and depleted antioxidant enzymes (SOD, CAT, GSH). CPSE treatment significantly normalized these parameters and preserved myocardial histoarchitecture. These findings suggest that *Celastrus paniculatus* exerts potent antioxidant, thrombolytic, and cardioprotective effects, supporting its potential as a natural therapeutic agent for cardiovascular disorders.

Keywords: Antioxidant activity, Cardioprotective activity, *Celastrus paniculatus* Willd., *In-vitro* thrombolytic activity, isoproterenol, myocardial infarction.

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the foremost cause of global mortality, accounting for nearly one-third of all deaths worldwide. Among the various manifestations, myocardial infarction, ischemia–reperfusion injury, and thromboembolic disorders are predominant contributors to morbidity and mortality. The underlying pathology is often linked with the formation of atherosclerotic plaques, endothelial dysfunction, and thrombus formation within the coronary arteries. Thrombosis, in particular, is a life-threatening condition characterized by the formation of intravascular clots, leading to impaired blood circulation and tissue necrosis [1, 2].

Although modern thrombolytic agents such as streptokinase, urokinase, and recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) have shown remarkable efficacy in dissolving blood clots, their use is constrained by limitations including short biological half-life, high cost, limited availability, and severe side effects such as hemorrhagic complications and allergic reactions [3]. Similarly, synthetic cardioprotective agents, while effective, may lead to adverse outcomes including arrhythmia, hypotension, or drug-induced toxicity. These challenges necessitate the exploration of safer, more effective, and economically viable therapeutic alternatives [4].

Emerging evidence suggests that oxidative stress, characterized by the overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS), plays a central role in myocardial ischemia and reperfusion injury. Excess ROS disrupts cellular homeostasis, leading to lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and apoptosis of cardiac myocytes. Modulating oxidative stress through antioxidants has therefore been recognized as a key therapeutic approach in cardioprotection [5].

Medicinal plants, enriched with diverse phytochemicals such as flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, and sterols, offer a natural reservoir of antioxidants with significant pharmacological potential. Several plant extracts have demonstrated fibrinolytic and cardioprotective activities, thus supporting their development as alternative or complementary therapies for cardiovascular disorders [6].

Celastrus paniculatus Willd., belonging to the family Celastraceae, is an indigenous medicinal plant distributed in India, Sri Lanka, and Southeast Asia. It is traditionally known as “Malkangni” or the “Intellect tree.” In Ayurvedic and Siddha medicine, its seeds and oil have been employed for centuries to enhance memory, alleviate mental fatigue, treat arthritis, and manage inflammatory conditions. Beyond its nootropic uses, ethnobotanical records indicate its applications in treating rheumatism, gout, bronchitis, and nervous system disorders [7].

The seeds of *C. paniculatus* are rich in biologically active compounds including alkaloids (celastrine, paniculatine), sesquiterpenes, triterpenoids, sterols, and polyunsaturated fatty acids. Recent pharmacological investigations highlight its neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and hepatoprotective properties. However, limited scientific evidence exists regarding its potential role in thrombolysis and cardioprotection, despite its strong phytochemical background suggesting such benefits [8]. Although *C. paniculatus* has been extensively used in traditional medicine, its thrombolytic and cardioprotective activities remain underexplored in systematic experimental models. Establishing its efficacy in these domains could provide a strong scientific basis for its use as a complementary or alternative therapeutic option for managing cardiovascular diseases.

Materials and Methods

Preparation and Extraction of *C. paniculatus* seeds

The botanically identified and authenticated seeds of *C. paniculatus* were collected from MG Naturals, Chennai. Then the dried seeds were coarsely powdered by a mechanical grinding and sieved (mesh no. 40). The powdered materials were then extracted with 70% v/v methanol, by continuous hot percolation techniques using soxhlet apparatus until the siphon tube cleared. After completion of the extraction, it was filtered and dried at 60°C in a rotary evaporator to produce a semisolid mass. The dried extract was stored at 4°C in an airtight container until further use.

Qualitative analysis

The *C. paniculatus* seed methanolic extract (CPSE) was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening for the identification of presence or absence of phytoconstituents by the standard procedures [9].

***In vitro* Thrombolytic analysis**

The *in-vitro* thrombolytic activity of *C. paniculatus* seed extract was carried out by the methods of Dagainawala HF *et al.*, 2006 with slight modification using streptokinase (SK) as a standard reference [10].

Blood Collection

Whole blood (3 ml) was drawn from healthy human volunteers (n = 3) without a history of oral contraceptive or anticoagulant therapy. Which was equally (500 µL each) transferred to six previously weighed micro centrifuge tubes and incubated at 37° C for 45 min and was allowed to form clots.

Effect of *C. paniculatus* extract on clot lysis

After clot formation, the serum was finely and completely aspirated without disturbing the clot and the tubes were again weighed to determine the clot weight.

Clot weight = Weight of the tube containing clot – Weight of the empty tube

The containing clot tubes were categorized, as a negative non thrombolytic control, about 100 µl of distilled water was added, as a positive control, 100 µl of streptokinase solution was added and 100 µl of various concentration of methanolic seed extract of *C. paniculatus* (i.e. 0.5mg/ml, 2.5 mg/ml, 5.0 mg/ml and 10.0 mg/ml) were added separately. At last, all the tubes were incubated at 37°C for 90 min. After incubation, released fluid was removed and tubes were again weighed to observe the difference in weight after clot disruption. Difference in weight before and after clot lysis was expressed as percentage of clot lysis [11]. Evaluation of thrombolytic effects of CPSE was performed by the formula below:

$$\% \text{ of clot lysis} = (\text{Weight of released clot/clot weight}) \times 100$$

The trial was repeated 3 times with the blood samples from the 3 different healthy volunteers. Various concentrations of CPSE i.e. 0.5mg/ml, 2.5 mg/ml, 5.0 mg/ml and 10.0 mg/ml were tested at various time intervals including; 24hrs, 48hrs and 72hrs duration of incubation at 37^o C for maximum clot lysis [12].

Acute oral toxicity studies

The acute oral toxicity of *C. paniculatus* seeds methanolic extract (CPSE) was evaluated by the acute toxic class method as per OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) test guideline 423 [13]. Three non-pregnant female rats were treated with a single oral dose of 2000 mg/kg CPSE. After administration, each animal was individually observed for the first 30 minutes, followed by special attention for the first 4 hours and periodically for 24 hours, thereafter daily for 14 days. The evaluation parameters include changes in skin and fur, mucous membrane, eye, respiration, circulatory, central, peripheral nervous system, somatomotor activity, behavioral changes and mortality.

In vivo* cardio protective study*Experimental animals**

The twenty four albino wistar rats (200-300 gm) were obtained from Central Animal house of Sri Abirami College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore. The animals were kept under standard environmental conditions of 12/12 light/dark rhythm, maintained under controlled room temperature ($23\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and a relative humidity of $60\pm 10\%$, in polypropylene cages. They were fed with a standard pellet diet and water *ad libitum*. The immature animals were acclimatized under laboratory conditions three days prior to initiation of the experiment. The cages were cleaned daily by changing the husk bedding. The experimental protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC) of Sri Abirami College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore; Care and use of laboratory animals were confirmed to CPCSEA guidelines.

IAEC Reference No: SACOP/Re/M. Pharm/05/2025 Dated: 21.06.2025

Experimental design

The mature twenty four albino wistar rats were divided into four groups of each six. Group I served as normal control received distilled water (1 ml/kg, *p.o.*) daily for 21 days and in addition received distilled water (0.5 ml/kg, *s.c.*) on the 20th and 21st day at an interval of 24 hr.), group II served as disease control, group III - IV served as treatment groups received CPSE 200 mg/kg & 400 mg/kg respectively for 21 days.

Induction of Myocardial Infarction Using Isoproterenol

Myocardial infarction was induced to the group II to IV by administering isoproterenol hydrochloride (dissolved in normal saline) subcutaneously (*s.c.*) for the two consecutive days into rats at an interval of 24 hr (20th and 21st day of study) [14].

Biochemical analysis

Twelve hours after isoproterenol last dose, all the rats were anesthetized with thiopental sodium (40-90 mg/kg, *i.p*) and the blood sample was collected by via retro-orbital sinus and the serum was separated for the estimation of marker enzymes.

Serum Lipid Profile Analysis

The serum lipid profile, was measured by estimating low-density lipoprotein (LDL), high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, triglyceride (TG) and total cholesterol were analyzed by using the semi-auto analyzer kits techniques following the manufacturer's instruction (ARKRAY Healthcare Pvt. Ltd., Surat, India). The kits code are LDL cholesterol (71LS400-56), HDL cholesterol (71LS300-56), and triglyceride (72LS100-60).

Serum cardiac specific injury markers analysis

The cardiac specific injury markers such as troponin I (cTnI), creatine phosphokinase-MB (CK-MB), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), alanine transaminase (ALT), aspartate transaminase (AST) and alkaline phosphate (ALP) in serum were estimated using commercially available kits (AGAPPE Diagnostics LTD, Kerala, India). The estimation was carried out as per the standard kit instruction in semi auto analyzer.

Heart tissue protein and antioxidant assay**Preparation Heart tissue homogenate**

The heart was dissected out immediately after scarification; washed with ice-cold saline. Cardiac tissue pieces were isolated, weighed and homogenized (10% w/v) in a chilled Tris buffer (10 mM, pH 7.4), centrifuged at 10,000g for 20 min in a high speed cooling centrifuge (0°C). Clear supernatant was used for the assay following cardiac antioxidant and tissue protein.

Lipid peroxidation (LPO) assay

The heart tissue lipid peroxidation, the concentration of MDA levels was determined by thiobarbituric acid (TBA) method [15]. A volume of 0.2 mL homogenate was pipetted into a test tube, followed by the addition of 0.2 mL of 8.1% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), 1.5 mL of 30% acetic acid (pH 3.5) and 1.5 mL of 0.8% TBA. Tubes were boiled for 60 min at 95°C and then were cooled on ice. Distilled water (0.1 mL) and 5.0 mL of n-butanol: pyridine (15:1 v/v) mixture were added to the tubes and centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 10 min. The absorbance of the developed color in the organic layer was measured at 532 nm. Levels of MDA were expressed as nmol g/tissue.

SOD assay

The SOD activity was determined in the supernatant using the nitro blue tetrazolium by method of Kakkar *et al.*, [16]. This method employs xanthine and xanthine oxidase to generate superoxide radicals which react with 2-(4-iodo-phenyl)-3-(4-nitrophenole)-5-phenyl-tetrazolium chloride (INT) to form a red formazan dye. The SOD activity is then measured by the degree of inhibition of this reaction. One unit of SOD is that which causes a 50% inhibition, based on the 50% inhibition of the formation of NADH- phenazine methosulfate-nitroblue tetrazolium formazan at 520nm. One unit of the enzymes is taken as the amount of enzyme for 50% inhibition of NBT reduction/min/mg protein.

Reduced glutathione (GSH) assay

Reduced glutathione (GSH) content was determined via the method of Ellman [17]. GSH determination is based on the development of yellow colour when 5, 5' dithio 2-nitro benzoic acid (DTNB) is added to compounds containing sulphhydryl groups. The values are expressed as nmoles g/wet tissue.

Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) assay

Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity was assayed via the method of Rotruck [18] with a modification: a known amount of enzyme preparation was incubated with H₂O₂ in the presence of GSH for a specified time period. The amount of H₂O₂ utilized was determined via the method of Ellman [17] The values are expressed as μ moles of GSH utilized/min/mg Hb or protein.

Catalase assay

The activity of catalase was determined in 3 mL of reaction media, which contained 2 mL of homogenizing medium (phosphate buffer; pH 7.0) in a test tube followed by 1 mL of H₂O₂ solution [19]. The blank was composed of one mL buffer pH 7.0 and 2 mL tissue homogenate (pH 7.0). The extinction was measured at a wavelength of 240 nm using ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer. The catalase activity was expressed as U mg/ protein.

Histopathological studies

Histological evaluation was performed on the lower portion of the heart tissue. After scarification the hearts were rapidly dissected and immediately washed with saline before being fixed in 10% formalin for 24 hr. The fixative was removed by washing through running tap water overnight. After dehydration through a graded series of alcohols, the tissues were cleaned in methyl benzoate, embedded in paraffin wax. Sections were cut into 5 μ m thickness and stained with hematoxylin and eosin and observed under light microscope with 40x magnification for histological changes.

Statistical Analysis

The results of all the groups are shown as mean values \pm standard error mean (mean \pm SEM). The data were analyzed by using Graphpad Prism V.8.0 statistical package. Statistical analyses of biochemical data were performed using a one-way ANOVA followed by a Tukey's post hoc test. P value of <0.05 was accepted as indicating statistical significance.

Results

Extraction Value and Phytochemical analysis

The *Celastrus paniculatus* seed methanolic extract cumulative extraction value was calculated as 14.4% w/w yield percentage. The primary phytochemical screening of *C. paniculatus* seeds methanolic extract (CPSE) showed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, steroids, glycosides, proteins, tannins, phenols, terpenes & steroids.

In vitro thrombolytic analysis of *C. paniculatus* seed extract

In the standard group 100 µl of streptokinase was added to the formed clots which showed higher percentage lysis of the clot [$90.00 \pm 4.50\%$] at 72 hrs of incubation. Negative control showed maximal negligible clot lysis [$4.50 \pm 0.40 \%$] at 72 hrs. A significant value ($P < 0.001$) was obtained by calculating the mean difference in the clot lysis (%) between streptokinase (positive control) and distilled water (negative control). When different concentration (0.5mg/ml, 2.5 mg/ml, 5.0 mg/ml and 10.0 mg/ml) of *C. paniculatus* seeds extract (CPSE) were used to treat clots, the maximal lysis of clot was (59.74 ± 2.40) %, (64.48 ± 0.45) %, (75.25 ± 1.64) %, and (86.00 ± 2.41) %, respectively at the incubation time of 72hrs. The significant mean percentage clot lysis was observed in the 5.0 mg/ml and 10.0 mg/ml of CPSE as compared to the negative control. However, CPSE showed concentration dependent clot lysis activity (Table 1&Figure 1).

Table 1: Maximum *In vitro* Thrombolytic analysis of *C. paniculatus* seed extract

Sample	Concentration	Clot lysis (%)
Control (Distil water)	100 µl	4.50 ± 0.40
Standard (Streptokinase)	100 µl	99.00 ± 2.87^c
CPSE	0.5 mg/ml	59.74 ± 2.40^{cf}
	2.5 mg/ml	64.48 ± 0.45^{cd}
	5.0 mg/ml	72.25 ± 1.64^c
	10.0 mg/ml	86.00 ± 2.41^c

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, N=3, Statistical significance represented as ^aP<0.05; ^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Control. ^dP<0.05; ^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Standard. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison tests

Figure 1: *In vitro* thrombolytic effect of methanolic seed extract of *C. paniculatus*. (A) Control (Distilled water), (B) Standard (Streptokinase), (C) CPSE 0.5 mg/ml, (D) CPSE 2.5 mg/ml, (E) CPSE 5.0 mg/ml, (F) CPSE 10.0 mg/ml

Acute oral toxicity study

The acute oral toxicity results of *C. paniculatus* seed extract showed that the 2000 mg/kg single dosing revealed that no toxic symptoms, mortality, observational, behavioral and somatomotor changes were observed. These results indicate that the CPSE was found to be safer for acute use at the tested dose level of 2000 mg/kg. Hence the lethal dose of 50% (LD50) of CPSE is greater than 2000 mg/kg. Based on the body surface factor 1/10th of the tested maximum (2000 mg/kg) acute oral toxicity dose of 200 mg/kg was selected as the low dose, twofold higher than the low dose 400 mg/kg was selected as the high dose further *in vivo* studies.

Effect of *C. paniculatus* seed extract on isoproterenol-induced changes in serum lipid profile

The results table 2 showed the effect of CPSE on isoproterenol induced changes in serum lipid profile. The level of serum total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL significantly increases and decreases in the levels of HDL in isoproterenol treatment as compartment to control group. The pre-treatment of CPSE however, significantly restored the lipid profile to near normalcy as compared to the negative control. The treatment of CPSE showed a dose dependent normalization effect on changes in serum lipid levels.

Table 2: Effect of *C. paniculatus* seed extract on isoproterenol-induced changes in serum lipid profile

Treatments	TC (mg/dl)	TG (mg/dl)	HDL (mg/dl)	LDL (mg/dl)
Group-I (Vehicle Control)	159.08 ± 4.98	89.42 ± 3.20	38.47 ± 2.42	102.73 ± 6.38
Group-II (Isoproterenol-85 mg/kg, <i>s.c.</i>)	186.63 ± 5.20 ^b	154.50 ± 5.46 ^c	23.30 ± 2.13 ^a	132.43 ± 8.65 ^b
Group-III (CPSE – 200 mg/kg <i>p.o.</i>)	160.47 ± 8.42 ^d	108.83 ± 6.74 ^a	30.28 ± 6.03	108.42 ± 4.20 ^d
Group-IV (CPSE – 400 mg/kg <i>p.o.</i>)	154.02 ± 4.29 ^e	93.25 ± 5.28 ^f	36.70 ± 4.10 ^d	98.67 ± 5.71 ^e

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^aP<0.05; ^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Group I. ^dP<0.05; ^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison tests

Effect of *C. paniculatus* seed extract on isoproterenol-induced changes in Serum cardiac specific injury markers

The activities of cardiac functional marker enzymes (CK-MB, Tnl, LDH, AST, ALT and ALP) in the serum of isoproterenol alone treated groups shown significantly (P<0.001) increased as compared to the normal control group rats. Though the pretreatment of CPSE (200mg/kg & 400

mg/kg) treated groups significantly prevented the depletion of myocardial enzymes as compared to the negative control. CPSE pretreatment dose dependently protects the isoproterenol induced myocardial injury. CPSE 400 mg/kg treatment showed high significant action on cardiac protection (Table 3a & b).

Table 3a: Effect of *C. paniculatus* seed extract on isoproterenol-induced changes in Serum cardiac specific injury markers

Treatments	CK-MB (IU/L)	Tnl (ng/mL)
Group-I (Vehicle Control)	96.83 ± 12.50	49.50 ± 6.03
Group-II (Isoproterenol-85 mg/kg, <i>s.c.</i>)	487.64 ± 27.15 ^c	343.07 ± 4.63 ^c
Group-III (CPSE – 200 mg/kg <i>p.o.</i>)	287.45 ± 14.01 ^{cf}	212.77 ± 5.74 ^{cf}
Group-IV (CPSE – 400 mg/kg <i>p.o.</i>)	204.24 ± 12.45 ^{cf}	105.50 ± 3.87 ^{cf}

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^aP<0.05; ^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Group I. ^dP<0.05; ^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison tests

Table 3b: Effect of *C. paniculatus* seed extract on isoproterenol-induced changes in Serum cardiac specific injury markers

Treatments	AST (IU/L)	ALT (IU/L)	ALP (IU/L)
Group-I (Vehicle Control)	42.63 ± 4.12	38.70 ± 6.43	33.14 ± 2.34
Group-II (Isoproterenol-85 mg/kg, <i>s.c.</i>)	109.20 ± 6.87 ^c	94.12 ± 4.70 ^c	48.63 ± 3.21 ^b
Group-III (CPSE – 200 mg/kg <i>p.o.</i>)	60.24 ± 5.26 ^{bf}	56.47 ± 8.60 ^{bc}	40.38 ± 3.78 ^a

Group-IV (CPSE – 400 mg/kg <i>p.o</i>)	50.87 ± 4.42 ^f	47.32 ± 4.26 ^f	31.54 ± 3.89 ^e
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Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^aP<0.05; ^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Group I. ^dP<0.05; ^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison tests

Effect of *C. paniculatus* seed extract on isoproterenol-induced changes in cardiac tissue antioxidants

In ISO control group, the administration of ISO injections significantly ($p < 0.001$) decreased the activities of endogenous antioxidant enzymes; superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione reductase (GRx), glutathione peroxidase (GSHPx), catalase (CAT) and significant ($P < 0.001$) increased level of lipid peroxidation (LPO) in heart as compared to normal control group (Table 4). However, the treatment with CPSE (200 and 400 mg/kg) significantly prevented the alteration in the activities of antioxidant enzymes; LPO, SOD, CAT, GRx and GSHPx as compared to ISO control group. The treatment of CPSE showed a dose dependent effect on the cardiac tissue antioxidant effect.

Table 4: Effect of *C. paniculatus* seed extract on isoproterenol-induced changes in cardiac tissue antioxidants

Group	Group-I (Vehicle Control)	Group-II (Isoproterenol-85 mg/kg, <i>s.c.</i>)	Group-III (CPSE - 200 mg/kg <i>p.o.</i>)	Group-IV (CPSE - 400 mg/kg <i>p.o</i>)
Lipid peroxidation (LPO) (MDA nmol g ⁻¹ tissue)	5.21 ± 0.23	17.82 ± 0.98 ^c	10.45 ± 1.24 ^{ad}	6.14 ± 0.14 ^e
Superoxide dismutase (SOD) (enzyme required for 50% inhibition of NBT reduction/min/mg hemoglobin)	15.24 ± 1.54	2.60 ± 0.28 ^c	6.23 ± 0.54 ^{be}	13.90 ± 1.78 ^f
Glutathione reductase (µmoles/mg hemoglobin)	10.06 ± 2.34	4.84 ± 0.35 ^c	7.86 ± 0.49 ^e	9.42 ± 0.28 ^f

Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) (μ moles of CDNB-GSH conjugate formed/min/mg hemoglobin)	153.54 \pm 2.89	72.28 \pm 0.75 ^c	90.27 \pm 1.25 ^f	114.25 \pm 8.32 ^f
Catalase (CAT) (μ moles of H ₂ O ₂ utilized/min/mg hemoglobin)	24.60 \pm 2.12	8.39 \pm 0.32 ^c	14.52 \pm 1.52 ^e	20.16 \pm 1.57 ^f

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^aP<0.05; ^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Group I. ^dP<0.05; ^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison tests.

Histopathological observations

Histopathological examination of myocardial tissue from normal control animals exhibited clear integrity of myocardial membrane. Heart tissues from isoproterenol treated rats showed widespread myocardial structure, edematous intramuscular space and sub endocardial necrosis with capillary dilatation and leukocyte infiltration as compared to normal control rats. Pretreatment of CPSE 200mg/kg showed mild muscle separation and few inflammatory cells, CPSE 400 mg/kg treatment showed no change in histo-architecture of heart tissue as compared to normal control rats (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Histological Findings of Heart tissue (A) Normal control, (B) Isoproterenol (ISO) treated group, (C) CPSE 200 mg/kg +ISO, (D) CPSE 400 mg/kg + ISO. Black arrow shows cardiac muscle fibers with muscle separation, Red arrow shows edematous intramuscular space and inflammatory cells.

Discussion

Many of today's diseases including cardiac diseases have been linked to oxidative stress which is initiated by the reaction of free radicals with biological macromolecules such as proteins, lipids and DNA [20]. Oxidative stress plays a significant role in the development and progression of myocardial infarction (MI) by creating an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) and antioxidants, leading to damage to heart muscle cells, inflammation, and cardiac dysfunction. Strategies for the treatment of MI, which is one of the most prevalent and serious health problems because of high morbidity and mortality levels, have changed significantly during the last 2 decades. Therefore, the development of new therapeutic techniques including new drug and/ or natural agent discovery against the occurrence of MI and the prevention of MI-related complications is a popular research area in the whole world [21].

Isoproterenol (IP), a synthetic β -adrenergic agonist, by its positive inotropic and chronotropic actions increases the myocardial oxygen demand that leads to ischemic necrosis of myocardium due to myocardial hyperactivity and coronary hypotension in rats similar to that seen in human myocardial infarction. A number of patho-physiologic mechanisms have been outlined to explain the IP-induced myocardial damage, viz. altered membrane permeability, increased turnover of nor-epinephrine, and generation of cytotoxic free radicals. In addition, ISP administration reduces blood pressure that triggers reflex tachycardia, thereby increases myocardial oxygen demand [22, 23] Hence in this study MI was successfully induced by the administration of isoproterenol (85 mg/kg, *s.c.*) for two consecutive days at an interval of 24 hr.

Atherothrombotic diseases like myocardial or cerebral infarction occur owing to the development of thrombus that causes hindrance in the passage of vessels. Even, sometimes in critical conditions, patients die due to embolism. A number of earlier researches indicated that herbs and phytomedicines possessed thrombolytic activity [24]. Addition of 100 μ L streptokinase, a positive control (30,000 IU), to the clots and subsequent incubation for 72 hrs, showed 99.00% lysis of

clot. On the other hand, distilled water was treated as negative control which exhibited a negligible percentage of lysis of clot 4.50%. The mean difference in percentage of clot lysis between positive and negative control was found to be statistically ($P < 0.001$) significant. In this study CPSE displayed the highest thrombolytic activity (86 %) at 10 mg/kg among the tested concentrations. CPSE shows dose dependent graded increases in thrombolytic activity. The thrombolytic property of the *C. paniculatus* seed extract is due to the diverse composition of phytoconstituents including rich sources of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins and terpenoids.

The safety of the *C. paniculatus* seeds extract was evaluated by acute oral toxicity study as per OECD guideline 423. The CPSE did not show any toxic symptoms or mortality at the limit dose of 2000 mg/kg p.o., which showed that the CPSE is safe to use up to 2000 mg/kg.

Lipids play a key role in cardiovascular diseases, not only by way of hyperlipidemia and the development of atherosclerosis, but also by modifying the composition, structure and stability of the cellular membranes. A significant elevation in the total cholesterol, LDL and triglycerides, and also decreased HDL levels were observed in serum of isoproterenol treated rats. Increased total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, TG and decreased HDL cholesterol are associated with raised risk for myocardial infarction [25]. Phospholipids were found to be increasing in the serum of isoproterenol treated rats. These changes could be attributed to enhanced lipid biosynthesis by cardiac cyclic adenosine monophosphate [26]. A strong positive correlation has been documented between the risk of developing ischemic heart disease and serum LDL level, whereas a negative correlation has been reported with HDL-cholesterol. The increase in serum phospholipids may be due to an increased peroxidation of membrane phospholipids released via phospholipase A₂ [27], which in turn decreased the phospholipid levels in heart tissue. The pre-treatments with CPSE successfully restored the elevated triglycerides, LDL-cholesterol, total cholesterol levels and also increased the HDL cholesterol levels in serum at a dose dependent manner. It shows the promising lipid lowering effect of CPSE in myocardial ischemic conditions.

Isoproterenol induced myocardial necrosis has been reported to alter membrane permeability and to cause leakage of marker enzymes of cardiac damage (LDH, CK-MB, Tnl, AST, ALT and ALP) into the blood stream [28]. Significantly elevated levels of these marker enzymes have been recorded in Isoproterenol induced myocardial damage [29]. Result of this study assures that

significant elevated levels of marker enzymes LDH, CK-MB, Tnl, AST, ALT and ALP in the IP alone treated group as compared to the normal control. On the contrary, CPSE treatment protected the structure and functional integrity of myocardial membrane as evident from the significant reduction in the elevated levels of these serum marker enzymes in the rats when compared to the isoproterenol treated rats. Increase in the activity of these enzymes is diagnostic indicators of myocardial infarction and are indicative of cellular damage and loss of functional integrity of cell membrane [30, 31]. The reversal of these enzyme activities by pretreatment with CPSE indicates its therapeutic potential against myocardial infarction in a dose dependent manner by preventing the Isoproterenol induced leakage of marker enzymes.

Our result shows that *C. paniculatus* seed extract treatments maintained the levels of lipid peroxides and antioxidants of the heart in myocardial infarcted rats. In our study an increase in the concentration of tissue TBARS was observed, which has been suggested to be due to an enhanced oxidative stress in experimentally induced myocardial injury. Oral treatment with CPSE significantly decreased the concentration of TBARS in the isoproterenol-induced rats. CPSE protects the heart against lipid peroxidative damage by removal of excess free radicals generated by isoproterenol. The presence of phenolic groups in phytochemicals of CPSE probably protected the heart from myocardial damage by scavenging free radicals and thereby suppressing the peroxidation of lipids.

SOD and CAT are considered as primary enzymes since they are involved in the direct elimination of ROS. We have observed a significant decrease in the activities of SOD and CAT in the isoproterenol-induced rats; this might be due to excessive generation of free radicals by isoproterenol. Administration of CPSE restored dose dependently the levels of SOD and CAT to near normal. This shows the antioxidant effect of CPSE against myocardial injury caused by free radicals.

Significant decrease in the level of GSH and Gpx may be due to its increased utilization during the burst of reactive oxygen species production, in protecting the 'SH' group containing proteins from lipid peroxidation [32]. The decreased activities of glutathione peroxidase in the heart of isoproterenol-induced myocardial infarction might be due to decreased availability of their substrate, reduced glutathione. Inactivation of the enzyme Gpx in the heart tissue leads to the

accumulation of oxidized glutathione which in turn inactivates many enzymes containing SH groups. Administration of CPSE significantly prevented the alterations in the levels of GSH, GPx and restored the levels to near normal. This effect may be due to the free radical scavenging properties of CPSE [33]. The scavenging activities of the phenolic substances are attributed to the active hydrogendonating ability of the hydroxyl substitutions [34]. The presence of the phenolic groups in the phytochemicals in *C. paniculatus* seeds could be responsible for .OH radical scavenging activity. Thus, it is quite clear that changes observed in SOD, CAT, GPx and GSH could be attributed to the enhancement in antioxidant status in tissues of normal rats.

Histopathological examination of myocardial tissue in control illustrated clear integrity of the myocardial cell membrane and no inflammatory cell infiltration was observed. Isoproterenol injected rats showed coagulative necrosis, separation of cardiac muscle fibres and infiltration of inflammatory cells. The reduced inflammatory cell infiltration and normal cardiac muscle fibre architecture further in the CPSE 400 mg/kg treatment confirmed the cardioprotective effect of CPSE in a dose dependent manner.

In conclusion these findings of this study scientifically validate the traditional claims of *Celastrus paniculatus* in cardiovascular disorders. The methanolic seed extract exhibits significant thrombolytic, antioxidant, and cardioprotective activities, supporting its potential as a natural therapeutic agent against thrombosis and myocardial injury. While the results are promising, further studies focusing on bioactive compound isolation, molecular mechanisms, pharmacokinetics, and clinical validation are essential to establish its translational application in cardiovascular disease management.

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